

RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN LEVELS OF NITROGEN COMPOUNDS WITH ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES AND SEMEN QUALITY IN BULLS*

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SUMMARY: Fertility is a complex process, involving multiple interactions between the sperm cells and seminal plasma components. The composition of seminal plasma has great influence on the biological quality of semen, as expressed by sperm motility and viability. The aim of this study was to evaluate relationships between semen characteristics and major nitrogen biochemical components of bovine seminal plasma with antioxidant properties (total proteins, albumin, uric acid, urea). Semen samples from 30 breeding bulls were examined. First, basic measurements were performed – volume (ml), pH and concentration ($\times 10^6/\text{mL}$). Motility analysis was carried out using the CASA system; total protein, albumin, uric acid and urea concentration measurements were based on a colorimetric reaction of the target substance and a spectrophotometric detection at a specific wavelength. The correlation analysis revealed that the spermatozoa motility was positively correlated with total proteins ($r=0.5823$; $p<0.001$), albumin ($r=0.6768$; $p<0.001$) as well as with uric acid ($r=0.5106$; $p<0.001$). Besides, the highest concentration of proteins, albumin and uric acid was found in samples of the best quality. No significant results ($p>0.05$) were found in relation to urea. This study proves the importance of proteins, albumin and uric acid in the semen quality, as well as the crucial role of biochemical analysis of semen in relation to male fertility.

Key words: *bulls, spermatozoa, proteins, albumin, uric acid, urea.*

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INTRODUCTION

Artificial insemination has proven to be the most effective tool for genetic improvement of animals of zootechnical importance, especially in the cattle industry. The inspection and handling of semen is considered a key and essential step for assessing fertility and the successful use of semen. Knowledge of fertility in bulls is an objective of great importance for the production of bovine semen, which is achieved by good analysis of the semen, among other assessments. To design an ideal bovine semen analysis to properly assess and predict the fertility of an ejaculate is the goal of many specialists in the reproduction field (Alm-Packalén, 2009).

The seminal plasma mediates the chemical function of the ejaculate. Due to its slight alkalinity (light alkaline buffer) it is also responsible for creating a milieu beneficial for the spermatozoa in a vaginal surrounding that is normally maintained acidic. Other functions of the seminal plasma include activation and augmenting the spermatozoa motility as well as supplying nutrients for the sperm cells (Eghbali et al., 2008). Besides, the seminal plasma possesses a wide antioxidant system to scavenge reactive oxygen species (ROS) and prevent ROS related cellular damage (Sharma and Agarwal, 1996).

This extracellular fluid is a composite mixture of secretions that come from the male accessory reproductive organs (Elzanaty et al., 2007). The composition of seminal plasma has great influence on the biological quality of semen, as expressed by sperm motility and viability. These factors are directly related to the fertilization success. Determining of seminal plasma composition can help to understand the design requirements for preparing the appropriate artificial seminal plasma solutions for short-term storage or cryopreservation (Bozkut et al., 2009).

The protein constituents of seminal plasma long have been considered of importance in the maintenance of proper conditions for spermatozoa. In fact, in the practice of artificial insemination, various protein-containing systems such as milk, gelatin solution, and egg yolk, in addition to various chemical buffer systems, have been used as semen extenders (Stančić et al., 2002; Jonáková and Tichá, 2004).

Non-protein nitrogenous compounds such as ammonia, creatinine, urea and uric acid, the major end products of protein metabolism, are excreted via urine. These compounds are also found in semen, although at much lower concentrations than in urine (Hirsch et al., 1991). They are probably derived from two sources: local production (Ogino et al., 1979) and transudation from the circulation (Setchell, 1974).

Determinations of biochemical constituents with antioxidant ability of seminal plasma are needed for semen evaluation, since physical characteristics of semen alone are not completely satisfactory for semen appraisal in the current practice. Thus, the present study was aimed at studying the relationships between semen characteristics and the major nitrogenous biochemical constituents with antioxidant properties (total proteins, albumin, uric acid, urea) present in bovine seminal plasma.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Bovine semen samples were obtained from 30 adult breeding bulls (Slovak Biological Services, Nitra, Slovak Republic). The samples had to accomplish the basic quality criteria given for the corresponding breed. The semen was obtained on a regular

collection schedule using an plastic artificial vagina.

After collecting the samples were stored in the laboratory at room temperature (22-25 °C) and basic measurements were performed – volume (ml), pH and concentration ($\times 10^6/\text{mL}$). Motility analysis was carried out using the CASA system – SpermVision (MiniTüb, Tiefenbach, Germany) with Olympus BX 51 phase microscope (Olympus, Japan). Each sample was placed into Makler Counting Chamber (depth 10 μm ; Sefi-Medical Instruments, Izrael) and the percentage of motile spermatozoa (motility $> 5\mu\text{m/s}$) was evaluated.

Subsequently, the samples were centrifuged (15 min, 15 000 rpm, 4°C) to obtain the cell sediment and seminal plasma fraction. The fractions were separated, seminal plasma was transferred into 1.5 ml tubes and kept frozen (-80°C) until analysis.

All of the measurements were based on a colorimetric reaction of the target substance and a subsequent spectrophotometric detection at a specific wavelength.

Albumin concentration was measured using the BioLa Albumin commercial kit (PLIVA-Lachema, Brno, Czech republic). The measurement was based on a reaction between albumin and Bromocresol Green (BCG) at acid pH forming a complex, which was easy to detect photometrically at 578 nm.

Uric acid measurement was characterized by the oxidation of the substance leading to H₂O₂ and allantoin formation. The formed H₂O₂ was detected by reacting with N-ethyl-N-(2-hydroxy-3-sulphopropyl)-m-toluidine (TOOS) and 4-aminoantipyrine (AOD). The absorbance was measured at 550 nm. BioLa Uric Acid commercial kit (PLIVA-Lachema, Brno, Czech Republic) was used.

The total protein content was measured by the DiaSys Total Protein (DiaSys, Holzheim, Germany) commercial kit based on the Biuret method, where copper ions (copper sulphate) together with proteins formed a violet blue color complex in alkaline solution. The absorbance of the color was directly proportional to the concentration and measured at 540 nm.

Urea detection was based on the urease-GLDH enzymatic UV measurement. Urea with hydrogen peroxide formed ammonium, the reaction was catalyzed by urease. Subsequently, ammonium reacted with 2-oxoglutarate and NADH forming L-glutamate. The conversion was detected at 340 nm. Urea concentration was measured using the Urea DiaSys (DiaSys, Holzheim, Germany) commercial kit.

Albumin and uric acid were measured with the help of Genesys 10 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc, USA). Urea and total protein content were analyzed using the Microlab 300® photometer (Vital Scientific NV, Netherlands).

Statistical analysis of the results was carried out using the statistical program GraphPad Prism 3.02 (Graphpad Software incorporated, San Diego, California, USA). Results are quoted as arithmetic mean $\pm$ standard error of mean (SEM). Pearson's correlation coefficient (two tailed) test was used to examine correlations between all the parameters of semen. The comparison of semen parameters in the quality groups of samples was carried out by the Tukey's Multiple Comparison Test.

RESULTS

The results of the semen and seminal plasma evaluation in Table 1 show that the total protein content of the seminal plasma was $71.88 \pm 0.39\text{g/L}$, while albumin concentration was $14.66 \pm 0.11\text{ g/L}$. Mean uric acid level was recorded as $109.57 \pm 3.08\ \mu\text{mol/L}$

and urea concentration was detected at 3.91 ± 0.06 mmol/L (Tab. 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of bull semen (mean $\pm$ SEM; n = 30)

Ejaculate volume (mL)	6.77 ± 0.03
pH	6.64 ± 0.01
Sperm concentration (x 10 ⁶ cells/mL)	$2,682.50 \pm 39.47$
Motility (%)	85.73 ± 0.44
Total proteins (g/L)	71.88 ± 0.39
Albumin (g/L)	14.66 ± 0.11
Uric Acid (μ mol/L)	109.57 ± 3.08
Urea (mmol/L)	3.91 ± 0.06

The correlation analysis revealed that the spermatozoa motility was positively correlated with total proteins ($r=0.5823$; $p<0.001$), albumin ($r=0.6768$; $p<0.001$) as well as with uric acid ($r=0.5106$; $p<0.001$). No correlation was found between the motility and urea. The concentration was negatively correlated with all of the observed parameters, negative correlations were found with motility ($r=-0.4232$; $p<0.05$) and total proteins ($r=-0.4250$; $p<0.05$). No significant correlations ($p>0.05$) were found when observing pH and volume of the samples. Significant correlations were also observed between albumin, uric acid and total proteins ($r=0.3660$; $p<0.05$ and $r=0.6254$; $p<0.001$ respectively). Sperm concentration, volume and pH of the samples remained unaffected by the observed biochemical parameters of seminal plasma (Tab. 2).

Table 2. Correlations between the quality parameters of semen and biochemical parameters of seminal plasma

	Concentration	pH	Volume	Motility	Total Proteins	Albumin	Uric Acid	Urea
Concentration	1							
pH	0.1755	1						
Volume	0.06254	0.1522	1					
Motility	-0.4232*	0.05761	0.1181	1				
Total Proteins	-0.4250*	0.09988	-0.02784	0.5823***	1			
Albumin	-0.2163	0.1115	0.06680	0.6768***	0.6254***	1		
Uric Acid	-0.1418	0.05054	0.08649	0.5106**	0.1853	0.3660*	1	
Urea	-0.1451	0.1649	0.3483	-0.07899	-0.06220	-0.03632	-0.09377	1

The correlation analysis was based on the value of the correlation coefficient: $\pm 0.111 - \pm 0.333$: no correlation; $\pm 0.334 - \pm 0.666$: moderate correlation; $\pm 0.667 - \pm 0.999$: high correlation. * $p<0.05$; ** $p<0.01$; *** $p<0.001$.

In order to have a better insight of the results and make the range variances narrower, the samples were categorized in three groups of Excellent (Ex, $>90\%$ motile; $n=16$), Good (Go; $80-89\%$ motile; $n=8$) and Medium quality (Me; $<79\%$; $n=6$) according to their motility rates (Tab. 3).

Table 3. Average values of observed parameters in the quality groups (mean $\pm$ SEM)

	Ex (n=16)	Go (n=8)	Me (n=6)
Volume (mL)	6.44 $\pm$ 0.06	7.3 $\pm$ 0.10	6.49 $\pm$ 0.03
pH	6.69 $\pm$ 0.01	6.49 $\pm$ 0.03	6.45 $\pm$ 0.04
Concentration(x 10 ⁶ cells/mL)	2574.38 $\pm$ 69.91	2433.75 $\pm$ 56.57	3302.50 $\pm$ 311.58
Motility (%)	93.92 $\pm$ 0.14	85.89 $\pm$ 0.30 ^{a**}	63.66 $\pm$ 2.10 ^{b*** c***}
Total Proteins (g/L)	76.54 $\pm$ 0.63	70.24 $\pm$ 1.03	61.63 $\pm$ 2.29 ^{b*}
Albumin (g/L)	16.22 $\pm$ 0.18	13.81 $\pm$ 0.33	10.12 $\pm$ 0.43 ^{b*** c**}
Uric Acid (μ mol/L)	145.85 $\pm$ 5.69	99.55 $\pm$ 11.54	26.16 $\pm$ 1.53 ^{b*}
Urea (mmol/L)	3.58 $\pm$ 0.11	4.43 $\pm$ 0.27	4.08 $\pm$ 0.17

^a Ex vs Go, ^b Ex vs Mo, ^c Go vs Mo. * p<0.05; ** p<0.01; *** p<0.001.

Mean values for motility were recorded as 93.92 $\pm$ 0.14% in Ex, 85.89 $\pm$ 0.30% in Go and 63.66 $\pm$ 2.10% in Me groups, which were significantly (p<0.001) different. The highest concentration of proteins, albumin as well as uric acid were detected in Ex group (76.54 $\pm$ 0.63 g/L, 16.22 $\pm$ 0.18 g/L and 145.85 $\pm$ 5.69 μ mol/L respectively) while the lowest concentrations for all three parameters were recorded in the Me group (61.63 $\pm$ 2.29 g/L, 10.12 $\pm$ 0.43 g/L and 26.16 $\pm$ 1.53 μ mol/L respectively). Significant differences were observed especially when comparing the content of mentioned parameters between the Ex and Me group. The highest concentration of urea was detected in the Go group (4.43 $\pm$ 0.27 mmol/L) and the lowest concentration was in the Ex group (3.58 $\pm$ 0.11 mmol/L). No significant differences were detected in relation to this parameter. Also, no significant differences were observed when comparing the concentration, pH and volume of the samples in the quality groups.

DISCUSSION

Evaluation of the sperm quality provides information allowing zootechnicians to determine the optimal time for sperm collection and to devise optimal handling and storage protocols for sperm used in artificial fertilization (Baas et al., 1983). Semen volume, concentration and motility as well as composition of the seminal plasma are common parameters to assess sperm quality in animals (Alavi and Cosson, 2006), with sperm motility being the single most important parameter of semen quality. Therefore, this study was aimed to evaluate the relationship between semen quality parameters and selected nitrogen compounds (total proteins, albumin, uric acid and urea) in bovine seminal plasma which are known to have antioxidant properties.

Seminal plasma proteins participate in events that occur both in the male and the female reproductive organs. Mammalian seminal plasma is a complex mixture of secretions originated from the testis, the epididymis, and the male accessory sex glands (seminal vesicles, ampulla, prostate, bulbourethral glands). Seminal plasma is a very complex fluid containing a wide variety of both organic and inorganic components, among which proteins are an important part of the high-molecular-weight substances (Jonáková and Tichá, 2004).

The proteins secreted into seminal plasma may play an important role during sperm capacitation and fertilization (Rodríguez-Martínez et al, 1998) and may also serve to protect sperm from damage or to maintain their longevity. Seminal plasma

contains many proteins that seem to be important in providing a suitable environment for the survival and function of spermatozoa. Some of these proteins are secreted by the testis (transferrin; Zalata et al., 1996), epididymis (neutral-alpha glucosidase; Yeung et al., 1990), prostate (prostate-specific antigen; Siciliano et al., 2000) and seminal vesicles (Elzanaty et al., 2007). All these proteins are extensively studied in semen in an attempt to determine their physiological role and clinical relevance in the evaluation of male fertility (Chia et al., 2000). Our study confirms the crucial role of proteins on the semen quality. A significantly positive correlation ($r=0.5823$; $p<0.001$) was detected between the protein content and spermatozoa motility. Besides, the highest concentration of proteins was found in the Ex group (76.54 ± 0.63 g/L) and the lowest concentration was detected in the Me group (61.63 ± 2.29 g/L).

Apart from organ-specific proteins, seminal plasma is rich in other proteins, of various origins and functions. One of these proteins is albumin. In this regard, Lindholmer et al. (1974) claimed that most of the albumin in seminal plasma originates from the prostate. Others suggested a testicular and epididymal origin of seminal albumin (Orlando et al., 1988). Albumin is a highly soluble protein present in plasma (Roche et al., 2008), which transports metals, fatty acids, cholesterol, bile pigments, and drugs. It is a key element in the regulation of osmotic pressure and distribution of fluid between different compartments. In general, albumin represents the major and predominant antioxidant in plasma acting through its multiple-binding sites and free radical-trapping properties (Bourdon and Blache, 2001).

Few studies have addressed the issue of possible correlation between seminal plasma albumin and sperm quality. A weak positive significant correlation between albumin and semen volume, as well as sperm concentration, was reported (Chard et al., 1991). On the other hand, according to Lindholmer et al., 1974, no correlation between albumin and sperm motility was found. Our results show, that albumin has a positive influence on semen quality. Not only it showed to have a positive correlation to motility ($r=0.6768$; $p<0.001$), but it also has been found in larger amounts in the best quality samples (16.22 ± 0.18 g/L).

The main nitrogenous components of urine such as ammonia, urea, uric acid and creatinine also exist in seminal plasma (Hirsch et al., 1991). They are probably derived from local production and transudation from the circulation. Urea enters testicular semen from the bloodstream (Setchell, 1974). Spermatozoa oxidize amino acids from which they produce various metabolites. In bulls, uric acid is probably formed by oxidation of hypoxanthine and xanthine, both of which occur in the seminal vesicles (Leone and Santoianni, 1957). This metabolically inert end product of purine metabolism has been found to act as an important non-enzymatic antioxidant in the blood as well as in other body fluids like seminal plasma (Keel et al., 2002). It can act as an oxidisable co-substrate for any reactive oxidative species and thus can protect the important biomolecules from oxidative damage. It also helps to stabilize the antioxidant activity of ascorbic acid in the seminal plasma (Xu et al., 2004). Reflection of all such protective role of uric acid was also seen the study of Zhang et al. (2009). Highest levels of uric acid were found in normozoospermics followed by asthenoterato, oligoasthenoterato and azoospermics. Moreover, the authors found a positive correlation between seminal uric acid and seminogram parameters like sperm motility and morphology. These findings were similar to that observed by Xu et al. (2004). Regarding our results, uric acid was behaving in a similar way than albumin did. It had a significantly positive cor-

relation with the motility ($r=0.5106$; $p<0.001$), the highest uric acid concentration was detected in the Ex group (145.85 ± 5.69 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) and the far lowest concentration was present in the Me group (26.16 ± 1.53 $\mu\text{mol/L}$).

Meanwhile, insignificant results were observed when analyzing the content of urea. Urea is considered to be in a relationship with protein metabolism and total protein content, nevertheless we did not find any significant correlations with the quality parameters of semen samples and the highest content of urea was found in the samples of the Go group (4.43 ± 0.27 mmol/L). Equally, Ronquist et al. (1985) reported that urea concentrations in semen were not correlated to any of the sperm motility parameters. According to Crich and Jequier (1978), the observed reduction in spermatozoa motility in their study was more closely related to a reduced osmolality than to pH or urea concentration. Srivastava et al. (1984) examined the levels of urea in males divided as normal, azoospermic, infertile with different sperm numbers and vasectomized. Similarly to other studies, no significant difference in the levels of urea between any of the groups was revealed.

CONCLUSION

Fertilization in mammals is a complex process, involving multiple interactions between the sperm cells and the seminal plasma components of the ejaculate. The distribution of nitrogen compounds with antioxidant properties, such as proteins, albumin, uric acid and urea in semen and seminal plasma should be considered in the interpretation of results obtained in the evaluation of bull fertility. Success in predicting fertility is limited by spermatozoa characteristics, the process of fertilization, and approaches used for *in vitro* evaluation of seminal quality. This study demonstrates the importance of proteins, albumin and uric acid in the bovine semen quality. Additionally we can conclude that analysis of biochemical characteristics, especially of nitrogen substances and antioxidants in semen provides very useful information regarding artificial insemination and male fertility.

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UTICAJ AZOTNIH JEDINJENJA SA ANTIOKSIDATIVNIM SVOJSTVIMA NA KVALITET SPERME BIKA

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Izvod

Fertilitet je složen proces, koji uključuje interakciju spermatozoida i komponenata spermalne plazme. Sastav spermalne plazme ima velikog uticaja na biološki kvalitet sperme, meren stepenom progresivne pokretljivosti i preživljavanja spermatozoida. Cilj ovog rada je da se oceni povezanost između osobina sperme i osnovnih biohemijskih azotnih sastojaka semene plazme sa antioksidativnim svojstvima (ukupni proteini, albumin, mokraćna kiselina i urea). Ispitivani su uzorci sperme od 30 priplodnih bikova. Prvo su određeni volumen ejakulata (ml), pH i koncentracija spermatozoida ($\times 10^6/\text{mL}$). Pokretljivost je utvrđena upotrebom CASA sistema. Sadržaj ukupnih proteina, albumina, mokraćne kiseline i mokraće, određen je kolorimetrijskom reakcijom targetne supstance i spektrofotometrijskom detekcijom specifične talasne dužine. Korelaciona analiza pokazuje da je pokretljivost spermatozoida u pozitivnoj korelaciji sa sadržajem ukupnih proteina ($r=0.5823$; $p<0.001$), albumina ($r=0.6768$; $p<0.001$) i mokraćne kiseline ($r=0.5106$; $p<0.001$). Veća koncentracija proteina, albumina i mokraćne kiseline je ustanovljena u ejakulatima naj boljeg kvaliteta. Nije ustanovljena statistički značajna ($p>0.05$) povezanost koncentracije mokraće i stepena pokretljivosti spermatozoida. Dobijeni rezultati pokazuju visok uticaj sadržaja proteina, albumina i mokraćne kiseline na kvalitet sperme, kao i izuzetno važnu ulogu biohemijske analize sperme, u korelaciji sa fertilitetom mužjaka.

Ključne reči: bikovi, spermatozoidi, proteini, albumini, mokraćna kiselina, mokraća.

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